

Attitude of Government and Private School Teachers Towards their Profession

Dissertation Submitted to Osmania University in Partial Fulfillment for the
Award Degree of Master of Education
[2020-2022]

by

Asfiya Zareen Rahman
Enrollment No -162620709048

M.Ed. [2020-2022]

Under The Guidance Of
Mrs Syeda Tauqeer Fatima
Assistant Professor (M.A, M.Ed)

Ghulam Ahmed College of Education
Banjara Hills, Hyderabad, Telangana -5000873

CERTIFICATE

I hereby certify that the thesis titled “ Attitude of Government and Private School Teachers Towards their Profession” submitted by Mrs Asfiya Zareen Rahman Enrollment No 1626207090 is a bonafied research record of the work pursued by her, for the award of Master of Education under my supervision , and that the same has/is not been the basis for the award of any Degree, Associateship, Fellowship or other similar titles of the candidates

Mrs Syeda Tauqeer Fatima
M.A, M.Ed
Assistant Professor
Ghulam Ahmed College of Education

DATE

PLACE: HYDERABAD

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis titled “ **ATTITUDE OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS THEIR PROFESSION**” is original research carried out by me under the supervision of **Mrs Syeda Tauqeer Fatima , M.A, M.ed , Assistant Professor, Ghulam Ahmed College of Education, Hyderabad , Telangana ,India .** Further I declare the research has/is not been submitted to any other university or institution, in original or duplicate for the award of any Degree or Diploma.

ASFIYA ZAREEN RAHMAN
Enrollment No.1626207090
M.Ed [2020-2022]

DATE:
PLACE: HYDERABAD

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Praise to be Allah the almighty who has been kind enough in his blessings and helped accomplish my research work with ease.

At the outset I would like to express my deep gratitude to **Dr VIBHA ASTHANA**, Principal of Ghulam Ahmed College of Education for the cooperation and help provided to me doing my work and allotting me the research guide.

I would like to express my sincere appreciation and deeper gratitude to my Dissertation supervisor **Mrs Syeda Tauqeer Fatima**, Assistant Professor , Ghulam Ahmed College of Education, Hyderabad, who has been a tremendous support and mentor for me throughout my dissertation study.

I am profoundly thankful to **Mr N Suresh Babu**, Assistant Professor, Ghulam Ahmed College of Education for his inputs on statistics and analysis and guidance in completion of this research work.

I reserve my highest admiration to my beloved parents **Mr Laiq ur Rahman** and **Mrs Nasreen Jahan** for their blessings, moral support and dedication to educate me. I am also grateful to my siblings and friends who helped me in shaping my aspiration and have always been behind me at all the times supporting morally and encouraging constantly in my endeavours to do better.

I am also thankful ton the Principals and teachers of schools, who generously granted me permission and helped me in data collection in their institutions. Lastly and in no way least I sincerely express my gratitude to all the authors and researchers listed in the bibliography whose ideas, concepts, defintions, and research findings helped me in understanding the concepts, selection of the research problem and analyzing the data.

Asfiya Zareen Rahman

ABSTRACT

Attitude plays a very important role in the life of a teacher and teaching because children remain under their care in the most impressionable years of their lives and the attitude of teachers is bound to influence them. This influence is likely to remain throughout their lives Teaching is the best profession and attitude towards teaching is a psychological determinant where effective experience brings changes towards teaching. As we know that a teacher's attitude towards teaching profession may be positive or negative and definitely positive teaching attitude impacts positive effect towards students, institution, society and nation on the other hand negative teaching attitude harms and makes teachers' all efforts useless.

The purpose of the study was to find the attitude of government and private school teachers towards their profession. In, total 50 teachers participated in the study. There were 25 teachers belonging to government school (12 male, 13 female) and 25 from private school (13 male, 12 female) .

Teachers Attitude inventory scale by S.P Ahluwalia was used to determine the attitude of teachers. The data was interpreted using statistical procedures, Mean and standard Deviations were calculated for the entire sample with respect to all variables. In order to test the hypotheses, Independent sample t test with respect to gender and type of school and z test for two sample means was applied for 50 teachers of government and private schools.

The results of the data revealed that there is significant difference in the professional attitude of teachers of government and private school teachers. However there is no difference in the professional attitude of male teachers of both government and private schools, while there was a significant difference in the attitude of female teachers of government and private schools.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION
2. LITERATURE REVIEW
3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY
4. PARTICIPANTS
5. APPARATUS/TOOLS
6. PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION
7. SCORING
8. STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE
9. RESULT
10. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS
11. REFERENCES
12. TABLES
13. APPENDICES

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

Teaching is considered as a noble profession and teachers are supposed to enjoy a prestigious position in the society. It is observed that the professional attitude and socio-economic status of a teacher are relatively low in India. Professions like Engineering, Medical, Management etc. are the first choice of every student because of attractive salaries and respectful position in the society. The high respect and status once attached to teaching profession has lost somewhere due to inadequate services rendered by teacher education institutions. For improvement and effective growth of teacher education, the attitude and perception hold by teacher trainees towards the teaching profession play an important role. A teacher should be mentally prepared and positively attached to his teaching profession in order to have effective outcomes. An attitude is a mental state of readiness that are organized through experiences of an individual towards the objects or the situations. Teacher's attitude towards their educational practices is essential to determine their classroom effectiveness.

The teachers are assigned the noble teaching education work which help in bringing up our future guardians. The quality of education be determined by the quality of the teacher. And the main function of a teacher is to create learning environment in which the learners are motivated to learn. Teaching is an art and the quality of teaching depends on the love, dedication and devotion of the teacher towards the knowledge of the subject. The quality of teaching can't rise above the qualities of its teachers. An effective teacher can create such an environment. On the contrary an ineffective teacher just fails to provide the student with proper climate of learning. The role of teacher is presuming new dimensions due to technological progress and new perspectives of knowledge resulting from scientific innovations. The role and responsibilities of a teacher are infinite and limitless and the success of any educational system depends much on the requisite qualities of teacher. Hence, the quality of Teacher is therefore pivotal and has been globally acquired to be significantly associated with the quality of education in general and students' learning achievements in particular. The Education Commission 1964-66 observed, "Of all the different factors which influence its quality of education and its contribution to national development, the quality, competence and character of teachers are undoubtedly the most significant." NEP 2020 also urges, that teachers will really shape the future of our children - and, therefore, the future of our country', which means that teachers will have to play significant role in nation building by creating high quality human resources in their classrooms. The quality of education is a key factor in the education system. The quality of education is increasingly judged by focusing on the performance of the students, on what the students are learning, and how well they are learning. In this context, schools and teachers have additional responsibilities in shaping student behaviour. The basic functions that schools are required to perform in the compulsory education system vary from one case to another. However, apart from the specific needs of each time and place, the main purpose of the school is to ensure, on the one hand, student Introduction 2 achievement, on the other hand, to the equal enjoyment of opportunities by all students. Schools, especially today, are being asked to perform these tasks, looking at the challenges of our times, such as multiculturalism, technological governance, the emergence of science and the rapid renewal of knowledge. At the same time, schools aim to prepare students not only for the present, but also for an ever-changing future. Thus, the role of the teacher in the society is vital for its improvement.

If teachers acquire professional competencies, teaching aptitude, attitude towards teaching and show great sense of responsibility in their work and if they are enabled and empowered to perform multiple tasks the result would be a high quality of teaching which will eventually lead to nation-building.

To be a thorough professional, you must think and act like a professional.

In learning scenario, teachers play a very important role. He /She plays the primary role in spreading the information and catering individual. How a teacher is dedicated and committed towards her profession plays a huge impact in shaping the young individual.

Commitment involves challenging yourself and by continuously imparting knowledge to students with a favourable attitude. In the process you are learning from your mistakes , learning from colleagues also from students thereby upgrading your knowledge and skills .Apart from mastery in your subject which you are dealing ,it is how you engage our students is what gives you an entirely different perspective to your teaching pedagogy. Learning journey is never a complete journey. Teacher should create an environment where learning is fostered and there is growth and all round development of child.

Instilling a desire for lifelong learning is one part, to channel them in positive direction, to shape their future and to know the purpose of education.

Teacher plays the centre figure in the field of education and can make the overall learning process more meaningful and interesting and strive for excellence for all round development of the society.

➤ *Attitude*

Attitude is familiar word and is used freely to express one's way of thinking, feeling or behaving. We say "he exhibits an attitude of friendliness or he has an Introduction 35 extremely favourable attitude towards teaching profession." What is exactly

meant by the term “attitude”? It is difficult to answer this question. It involves the definition of “attitude” and to define a psychological term in simple words is a difficult task. Attitude is outlined in specialized literature, particularly in the works of social psychology, on the basis of theories of Gordon Allport. Allport (1935) has suggested four common conditions for the formation of attitudes (i) The accretion and integration of responses learned in the course of growing up (ii) The individual differentiation or segregation of experiences, (iii) The influence of some dramatic experience or trauma and (iv) The adoption of readymade attitudes. Like most other abstract terms in English language, attitude has more than one meaning. The word attitude is derived from the Latin word “aptus” meaning apt, suited or prone. Generally, the term attitude nowadays is used in psychology to denote a certain preparedness to attend certain objects. No one is born with any attitudes. Attitudes such as interests are learned through life experiences that involve a person’s behaviour toward a person, profession, objects, problems, situations, etc. Attitudes in the character are very personal and complex. Attitudes are handled separately in each individual and the organization is the product of their own reactions to their experiences. Attitudes can significantly affect a person’s behaviour, and consequently, a person’s attitudes may be positive (favourable) or negative (unfavourable). Attitude towards teaching is a broad concept, having several dimensions in its interpretation. One dimension views teaching as a profession. Another dimension refers to the actual teaching process in classroom. A third dimension is linked to the client in the classroom- i.e. the pupils. This dimension may regard teaching as the interaction between teacher and pupils. A fourth dimension refers to the educational process.

➤ *Attitude Towards Profession*

The attitude of a teacher towards their profession is pivotal in the interaction between teacher and a student. Attitude towards the teaching profession is an emotional orientation, driven by teaching experiences to respond positively to teaching. It is a set emotional response towards teaching. People have a positive attitude towards objects that enable them to achieve value and a negative attitude towards objects that creates hurdles in attaining values. The teaching profession’s attitude is an important variable because it severely affects the effective expression of knowledge and skills appropriate to the teaching profession. In other words, we believe that there is a lack of positive attitudes towards the teaching profession, knowledge and skills, even if they are made at a very high level and do not express sustainability.

Knowing the attitude of an individual towards an object or a stimulus would make it possible to predict the behaviour of the same individual towards the related stimulus. When analysing teacher behaviour in the classroom environment, one of the main factors that determine teacher behaviour is the quality of the individual’s attitude toward the profession. Teachers play an important role in moulding students’ character, personality, behaviour, habits and manners (Agarwal, 2010). According to Brown (2001), teachers who are highly motivated and who have a positive attitude toward their profession may develop better relationships. Therefore, in order to succeed in a teaching profession that requires patience, dedication and continuous operation, it is important to volunteer and practice this profession. Teachers who were generally dissatisfied with the teaching profession reported that they were more concerned about their teaching status than enthusiastic teachers (Litt and Turk, 1985). Therefore, in order to improve the professional development and education of teachers, the policies they follow are vital. In a natural setup, the teacher is simply the setter of the stage, the supplier of materials and opportunities, the ideal environment, and the main factors that determine the success of any programme (Bichi, Embong & Mamat, 2015). Attitude can be defined as a trait to understand and motivate a person’s feelings toward a particular problem and to show positive or negative behaviour, so attitude gives direction to the behaviour (Kagitsibasi, 1988). Developing specifically for a professional attitude is the most important determinant of a person’s success in the profession (Cakir, 2005). Therefore, knowledge and skills in the field of a qualified teacher are inadequate, and attitudes toward the teaching profession must be positive (Cogan and Çoban, 2009). Attitudes toward the teaching profession play a key role in successfully completing the teaching profession (Ozbeck, Kahyoglu, & Ozen 2007; Taskin & Hasiomeroglu, 2010). The components of teacher’s attitude with each other sub attitudes is shown in the figure-1.11. . Numerous studies have shown that teacher attitudes affect student behaviour. Teachers have to do a very responsible job of assessing the characteristics of a future society and preparing people to fit into that community. Therefore, teachers are expected to have a positive attitude towards the teaching profession. Similarly, teachers have always been instrumental in social and national reconstruction and will continue to do so in the future. Teachers must have good teaching ability to fulfil these responsibilities and liabilities. The need of the hour is to have competent, committed and professionally well qualified teachers who can meet the demands of society.

Therefore, it is necessary to carry the present research in which investigator compares professional attitude of the teacher belonging to the government and private teacher education institutions in order to examine the difference in the quality of service. The findings from this study would bring qualitative and quantitative improvement in teacher education institutions and teaching-learning process. Therefore, future teachers will be benefited and it will give a food for thought for all those persons, authorities, policy makers, administrators who are attached or responsible for bringing improvement in teacher education institutions.

➤ *Significance of the study*

The old conception of the role of teacher has been transformed into a new concept, and the teacher is regarded as the agent of change, not merely the communicator of knowledge and culture. He is considered the transformer of the entire universe. It’s possible if he had that feeling. Globally, community expectations for teacher quality are increasing at a time when teacher status is declining (Moon, 2007). Disappointment for any person who is busy in business can lead to professional stagnation. A teacher without teaching competence, teaching aptitude, attitude towards teaching and a sense of responsibility, is a great loss not only to

himself but to society as a whole. The entire superstructure of the nation's educational setup is based on secondary education and requires understanding the current educational system and its development, content knowledge, teaching and contribution to the curriculum. Teacher is the main pillar in the education process. If he is skilled, honest, caring and confident we can be confident about the future of the country. In case he is half-hearted in doing his job, he cannot express himself and the nation cannot rely upon him. Teachers in government schools and need to upgrade their skills and to develop critical understanding of new policies and pedagogical changes applied. Old teaching techniques are still used in classrooms, failure of many training programmes and lack of proper attitude towards teaching and sense of responsibility among teachers is now the major area of concern. Thus, it becomes an attempt to work out whether secondary school teachers are really honest about their work, because at the moment a large number of teachers are not interested in their profession and they are only in the profession as a mechanical wage earner. Education is going to be more privatized and producing less quality. The last three decades were emphasised on quality of education and to enhance the quality of learning in schools, NCERT developed Learning Outcomes at the Elementary Stage (NCERT, 2017) and started process of developing learning outcomes for classes IX to XII (MHRD, 2018) at national level by enabling teachers to ascertain learning skills more accurately and take corrective steps without delay and provide effectual chances. Introduction 60 to learn to all students including children with special needs. Teachers will keep learning outcome at fore front and will use various teaching- learning resources because teacher quality is an important determinant of student's achievement. Bariana (2019) in his article says that from officials to Principals and teachers everybody admits that "Low Quality" classroom teaching continues to be Achilles heels of school education in the Punjab state. Hence, the quality of pedagogical inputs cannot be achieved without proper attitude among teachers.

Attitude towards teaching for the study means secondary school teachers' attitude towards professional behaviour, classroom teaching, personality attributes, beliefs of the teachers and professional aspirations.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Review of Literature*

A literature review is a survey of scholarly sources on a specific topic. It provides an overview of current knowledge, allowing you to identify relevant theories, methods and gaps in the existing research.

➤ *Meenu Malik*

A Comparative Study of Professional Attitude, Socio-Economic Status and Academic Background of Teacher Trainees in Government and Private Teacher Training Institutions.

➤ *Objectives*

- To Study the levels of professional attitude, socio-economic status and academic background of the teacher trainees.
- To compare the levels of professional attitude, socio-economic status and academic background of teacher trainees belonging to government and private teacher education institutions.

➤ *Findings*

- The present study revealed that 16.6% (137) of teacher trainees possess low professional attitude, 67.4% (555) have average professional attitude and only 15.9% (131) have high attitude towards teaching profession.
- As far as levels of socio-economic status are considered, it is found that 16.3% (134) of teacher trainees belong to the low socio-economic status, 69.1% (569) are in the category of average socio-economic status and 14.6% (120) possess high socio-economic status

B. *Ii. Annamalai (2000)*

Attitude of Teachers Towards Teaching of Teachers of High School and Higher Secondary School.

➤ *Objectives*

To study the attitude of teachers towards teaching on a sample of 400 high school and higher secondary school teachers (men, N=265) and (women, N=135).

➤ *Findings*

- The results of the study revealed that high school and higher secondary school teachers do not differ in their attitude towards teaching.
- Location of the school, age and level of teaching didn't have any influence upon the teacher's attitude towards teaching

C. *Iii. Jayakanthan (2003)*

Relationship between Teachers Attitude Towards Teaching and General Teaching Competence

➤ *Objective:*

To examine the relationship between attitude towards teaching and general teaching competence

➤ *Findings:*

- The study revealed that the government and aided school teachers differed in their attitude towards teaching.
- It revealed that government and aided school teachers differed significantly in their attitude towards teaching, that men and women teachers differed significantly in their attitude towards teaching, and that the general teaching competence of teachers and their attitude towards teaching were significantly related to each other and that age and qualification influenced teaching competence

D. *Iv. Hogörür Et Al. (2002)*

Relation between Class Level and Teaching Attitude

➤ *Objectives:*

To study the relation between the class levels and attitude.

➤ *Findings:*

A positive relation between the class levels and attitude. When the class level increases, pre-service teachers' attitude towards teaching profession rise, similarly.

E. V Bozdoan Et Al. (2007)
Pre-Service Teachers Attitudes Towards Teaching Profession

➤ Objectives:

To study the pre-service teachers’ attitudes towards teaching profession

➤ Findings:

The pre-service teachers’ attitudes towards teaching profession changed according to the gender and type of program they graduated from

➤ Title of the study: “A study on attitude of government and private school teachers towards their profession”

The major objectives of the study were

- To study the levels of professional attitude of the teachers
- To compare the level of professional attitude of teachers belonging to government and private school teachers.
- To compare professional attitude of male teacher belonging to government and private school teachers.
- To compare professional attitude of female teacher belonging to government and private schools.

➤ Major Findings of the Study were

- There is significant difference in the professional attitude of teachers belonging to government and private schools.
- There is no significant difference in the professional attitude of male teachers belonging to government and private schools.
- There is significant difference in the professional attitude of female teachers belonging to government and private schools.

➤ Hypothesis

- H0.: There is no significant difference in professional attitude of teacher belonging to government and private school teachers
- H0.1.1: There is no significant difference in professional attitude of male teacher belonging to government and private school teachers
- H0.1.2: There is no significant difference in professional attitude of female teacher belonging to government and private school teachers

➤ Method

In this chapter the research methodology used in the study is described. The sample selected, tools used, procedure adapted for data collection and the statistical techniques are being given in the order.

- The investigator followed “survey type” of the descriptive research. This method is more suitable for the purpose of investigation.
- In the present investigation the sample consisted of 50 secondary school teachers from government and private schools of Hyderabad district.
- In each group there were 12 male teachers and 13 female teachers.

➤ A Diagrammatic Representation of the Sample is given below:

Fig 1 A Diagrammatic Representation

To carry out the research of this type, keeping in mind the objectives and hypotheses of the study the following tools was selected in view of the nature and the objectives of the study.

➤ *Delimitations*

- The study is limited to the study of teachers attitude towards their profession of government and private schools of Hyderabad.
- The study is limited to 50 teachers from government and private schools
- The study was conducted only on school level teachers.

➤ *Tools*

Attitude inventory scale by S.P Ahluwalia was used. It is a standardized test. The following Table shows the number of favourable statements in this area. There are 7 favourable statements and 8 unfavourable statements related to attitude towards teaching profession. The investigator distributed the teacher attitude inventory (T.A.I) to each of the subject. This work has been undertaken in free periods of the subjects. They were given full information and instructions about T.A.I. It was also instructed to think in terms of general situations rather than specific ones.

➤ *Collection of Data:*

The researcher sought the permission of the institution and got the time to administer the test. Then the researcher distributed the inventory and gave necessary instructions about the inventory. The research and respondents to the doubts raised by the teachers while answering the inventory had developed a relationship with teachers and made sure the responses were true and natural by the individual asked them to respond promptly without any bias to make sure that data will be free from copying response from others. Likert continuum strongly agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree has been provided of each item-subject respond to each item putting a tick (✓) in the square of the chosen alternative against the serial number of the attitude statement in the answer sheet. Subjects are required to respond to all the items like-wise.

➤ *Scoring*

Each item alternatives assigned a weight arranging from 4 (strongly agree) to 0 (Strongly disagree). The attitude score of a subject is the sum total of items scores of favourable statement and unfavourable statement. Prepare the tables of scores for all samples (all teachers). Calculate the mean, standard deviation and relative standard deviation. Significance test at alpha 0.05 was done by the researcher using an independent t test. An independent t test is used to test the means of two different groups of the population. Lastly interpreting the results in terms of hypothesis.

➤ *Statistical Technique*

Statistical techniques are employed on the raw score to make it meaningful and to test the significance of the scores. Without use of statistical techniques raw scores do not have their own meaning and weight. 200 Different types of statistical techniques are available which can be used for statistical treatment, keeping in view the nature and objectives of the research problem researcher have used the following statistical techniques:

• *Mean*

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

- ✓ $\sum X$ = Sum of the Scores
- ✓ N = Number of the Scores

• *Standard Deviation*

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

• *T test for Independent Sample :*

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2}{(n_1 - 1) + (n_2 - 1)}\right)\left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2}\right)}}$$

$$df = n_1 + n_2 - 2$$

- *Z test for Two Sample Means*

$$z = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS

A. *Results:*

Analysis of the data means studying the tabulated material in order to determine facts or meanings.

This chapter analyses and interprets the data collected keeping in view the objectives and hypothesis of the study.

➤ *Table 1*

It is evident from table 1 that 50% of teachers are male and 50% of teachers are female.

The table shows age group frequency distribution to the age of teachers belonging to government school. Out of the 25 teachers of the government school selected for the study 11 teachers belong to the age group of 24-30 years, 8 teachers belong to 31-36 years, 4 teachers belong to the age group of 37-43 years and 2 teachers belong to the age group of 44-50 years.

It is thus evident that 44% of the teachers belong to the age group of 24-30 years, 32% of the teachers belong to the age group of 31-36 years, 16% of the teachers belong to the age group of 37-43 years and 8% of the teachers belong to the age group of 44-50 years.

The table shows age group frequency distribution to the age of teachers belonging to private school. Out of the 25 teachers of the private school selected for the study 8 teachers belong to the age group of 24-30 year, 7 teachers belong the age group of 31-36 years, 5 teachers belong to the age group of 37-43 years and 5 teachers belong to the age group of 44-50 years.

It is thus evident that 32% of teachers belong to the age group of 24-30 years while 28% of teachers belong to the age group of 31-36 years and there were 20% of teachers in both the age groups of 37-43 and 44-50 years.

The table shows management wise distribution of the sample. The entire sample of was drawn from two different managements which were identified according to the type of management. Thus it may be concluded that equal percentage of the sample was drawn from both the managements.

The table shows the distribution according to the teaching experience of the teachers. Out of the 50 teachers selected for the study 8 teachers had no experience followed by 13 teachers who had experience less than 3 years 19 teachers had experience between 4-9 years and 5 teachers had experience between 10-15 years. Also 5 teachers had experience of more than 16 years.

It is thus evident that 10% of the teachers had experience between 10-15 years and also 10% of the teachers had experience of more than 16 years while 38% of teachers had experience between 4-9 years, 26% of teachers had experience less than 3 years while 16% of teachers had no experience.

B. *Analysis of Significance of Mean Difference*

Analysis of significance of difference is an important procedure by which the researcher is able to make inferences involving the determination of statistical difference between groups with reference to selected variables. It involves the difference between mean of two groups the number of subjects in each the amount of variation spread present in the scores. Thus the t test and z test is used to determine whether the performance of two group is significant or not.

➤ *Z Test*

Z test has used to find out the significant differences in the mean score of professional attitude of teachers belonging to government and private schools.

➤ *T-Test*

T value has been used to find out the significant if differences in mean score of professional attitude of teachers with respect to the following sub samples.

- Gender
- Type of school

CHAPTER FOUR DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A. Discussion

For the present study the researcher had formulated three hypotheses.

➤ Hypotheses – 1

There is no significant difference in professional attitude of teacher belonging to government and private schools.

The table value reveals that 'z' value calculated for the attitude of teacher belonging to government and private schools is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 levels. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it is inferred that there is significant difference in professional attitude of teachers belonging to government and private schools.

➤ Hypothesis-2:

There is no significant difference in professional attitude of male teachers belonging to government and private school teachers.

The table reveals that the 't' value calculated for the professional attitude of male teachers belonging to government and private school is not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 levels, Hence null hypothesis is accepted. Hence it is inferred that there is no significant difference between the professional attitude of male teachers belonging to government and private schools.

➤ Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference in professional attitude of female teacher belonging to government and private school teachers.

The table reveals that the 't' value calculated for the professional attitude of female teachers belonging to government and private schools is significant at 0.05 and 0.01 levels. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. Hence it is inferred that there is significant difference between the professional attitude of female teachers belonging to government and private school.

➤ Findings:

- Majority of the teachers have favourable attitude towards their profession.
- By testing hypothesis one: it was revealed that there is significant difference between the professional attitude of teachers belonging to government and private schools.
- By testing hypothesis two: it was revealed that there is no significant difference in professional attitude of male teachers belonging to government and private school teachers
- By testing hypothesis three: it was revealed that there is significant difference in professional attitude of female teacher belonging to government and private school teachers

B. Conclusion:

The Indian tradition accords the highest place of respect and status to the Guru who is the remover of darkness, enlightens the individual and society and is considered to have wisdom coupled with spirituality. He is capable of leading humanity to divinity. The tradition of teachers of India and the indigenous education system of this country generated, created and disseminated knowledge and wisdom much ahead of others. A teacher has been worshipped and respected throughout human history because of his/her noble mission. Teachers are thus the greatest assets of any education system. They are accepted as the backbone of education system.

The real importance of teacher can be understood through these lines- "If a doctor commits a mistake, it is buried, if an engineer commits a 4 mistake, it is cemented, if a lawyer commits a mistake, it is filed, but when a teacher commits a mistake, it is reflected by the nation".

The teacher required to concern himself with the total development of the child and not only with one or two aspects a teacher's attitude towards teaching profession may be positive or negative and definitely positive teaching attitude impacts positive effect towards students, institution, society and nation on the other hand negative teaching attitude harms and makes teachers' all efforts useless.

Only satisfied and well adjusted teacher can think and do of the well being of the nation. Hence Teacher's attitude towards teaching may be positive or negative but are of great significance for the efficient and profitable functioning of any institution. Teachers who have positive attitude towards teaching have great satisfaction with their Jobs enjoy their profession and prefer teaching in spite of many economic or social abuses. On the other hand, teachers who have a negative attitude towards their teaching will not get satisfaction with their Jobs. They will not enjoy their profession and will be like a fish without water.

REFERENCES

- [1]. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/111177>
- [2]. www.academia.edu
- [3]. Researchbasics.education.uconn.edu
- [4]. www.real-statistics.com
- [5]. laugiwa.medium.com
- [6]. www.graphpad.com
- [7]. www.psychologydiscussion.net
- [8]. https://www.academia.edu/45301443/A_Study_of_Teachers_Attitude_Towards_Teaching_Profession

APPENDIX A –C TABLES

➤ *Appendix: A*

Table 1 Details of The Sample.

Management	Male	Female	Total
Government	12	13	25
Private	12	13	25
Total	24	26	50

Table 2 Details of Weightage for Favourable and Unfavourable Statements

ATTITUDE	WEIGHTAGE
Strongly agree	4
Agree	3
Undecided	2
Disagree	1
Strongly disagree	0

➤ *Appendix A1*

Table 3 Gender Wise Distribution of Sample

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	25	50%
Female	25	50%
Total	50	100

Table 4 Age Wise Distribution of Sample of Government Schools

Age Group	Male	Female	Total
24-30	3	8	11
31-36	4	4	8
37-43	3	1	4
44-50	2	-	2
Total	12	13	25

➤ *Appendix B1*

Table 5 Age Wise Distribution of Sample of Private School

Age Group	Male	Female	Total
24-30	2	6	8
31-36	4	3	7
37-43	4	1	5
44-50	2	3	5
Total	12	13	25

Table 6 Management Wise Distribution of Sample

Management	Frequency	Percentage
Government	25	50%
Private	25	50%
Total	50	100

➤ *Appendix B2*

Table 7 Showing Teacher Teaching Experience Wise Distribution of Sample

Teaching Experience	Government	Private	Total
None	5	3	8
Less than 3 years	6	7	13
4-9 years	10	9	19
10-15 years	1	4	5

More than 16 years	3	2	5
--------------------	---	---	---

➤ *Appendix C*

Table 8 Showing Calculated Value of 'T' of Professional Attitude of Teachers Belonging to Government and Private School Teachers

Sample	Sample Size	Mean	StandardDeviation	t
Government	25	43.72	6.181	
Private	25	47.56	6.090	2.2127

Table 9 Showing Calculated Value of 'T' of Professional Attitude of Male Teachers Belonging to Government and Private School

Sample	Sample size	Mean	StandardDeviation	t
Government	12	43.9	5.468	0.5455
Private	13	45.33	7.25	

Table 10 Table Showing Calculated Value of 'T' of Professional Attitude of Female Teachers Belonging to Government and Private School

Sample	Sample size	Mean	StandardDeviation	t
Government	13	43.5	6.995	2.724
Private	12	49.615	4.052	

APPENDIX D T-CRITICAL VALUE TABLE

Appendix D T –Critical Value Table

Critical values of *t* for one-tailed tests

Significance level (α)

Degrees of freedom (<i>df</i>)	.2	.15	.1	.05	.025	.01	.005	.001
1	1.376	1.963	3.078	6.314	12.706	31.821	63.657	318.309
2	1.061	1.386	1.886	2.920	4.303	6.965	9.925	22.327
3	0.978	1.250	1.638	2.353	3.182	4.541	5.841	10.215
4	0.941	1.190	1.533	2.132	2.776	3.747	4.604	7.173
5	0.920	1.156	1.476	2.015	2.571	3.365	4.032	5.893
6	0.906	1.134	1.440	1.943	2.447	3.143	3.707	5.208
7	0.896	1.119	1.415	1.895	2.365	2.998	3.499	4.785
8	0.889	1.108	1.397	1.860	2.306	2.896	3.355	4.501
9	0.883	1.100	1.383	1.833	2.262	2.821	3.250	4.297
10	0.879	1.093	1.372	1.812	2.228	2.764	3.169	4.144
11	0.876	1.088	1.363	1.796	2.201	2.718	3.106	4.025
12	0.873	1.083	1.356	1.782	2.179	2.681	3.055	3.930
13	0.870	1.079	1.350	1.771	2.160	2.650	3.012	3.852
14	0.868	1.076	1.345	1.761	2.145	2.624	2.977	3.787
15	0.866	1.074	1.341	1.753	2.131	2.602	2.947	3.733
16	0.865	1.071	1.337	1.746	2.120	2.583	2.921	3.686
17	0.863	1.069	1.333	1.740	2.110	2.567	2.898	3.646
18	0.862	1.067	1.330	1.734	2.101	2.552	2.878	3.610
19	0.861	1.066	1.328	1.729	2.093	2.539	2.861	3.579
20	0.860	1.064	1.325	1.725	2.086	2.528	2.845	3.552
21	0.859	1.063	1.323	1.721	2.080	2.518	2.831	3.527
22	0.858	1.061	1.321	1.717	2.074	2.508	2.819	3.505
23	0.858	1.060	1.319	1.714	2.069	2.500	2.807	3.485
24	0.857	1.059	1.318	1.711	2.064	2.492	2.797	3.467
25	0.856	1.058	1.316	1.708	2.060	2.485	2.787	3.450
26	0.856	1.058	1.315	1.706	2.056	2.479	2.779	3.435
27	0.855	1.057	1.314	1.703	2.052	2.473	2.771	3.421
28	0.855	1.056	1.313	1.701	2.048	2.467	2.763	3.408
29	0.854	1.055	1.311	1.699	2.045	2.462	2.756	3.396
30	0.854	1.055	1.310	1.697	2.042	2.457	2.750	3.385
40	0.851	1.050	1.303	1.684	2.021	2.423	2.704	3.307
50	0.849	1.047	1.299	1.676	2.009	2.403	2.678	3.261
60	0.848	1.045	1.296	1.671	2.000	2.390	2.660	3.232
70	0.847	1.044	1.294	1.667	1.994	2.381	2.648	3.211
80	0.846	1.043	1.292	1.664	1.990	2.374	2.639	3.195
100	0.845	1.042	1.290	1.660	1.984	2.364	2.626	3.174
1000	0.842	1.037	1.282	1.646	1.962	2.330	2.581	3.098
Infinite	0.842	1.036	1.282	1.645	1.960	2.326	2.576	3.090

